

Almost $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -Continuous Functions in Topological Spaces

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 27 July 2024</p> <p>Corresponding Author: T.D. Rayanagoudar</p>	<p>The literature in 1968, almost continuous functions were introduced by Signal and Signal [14]. This paper introduced, a new class of functions called almost $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$-continuous functions and faintly $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$-continuous functions in topological spaces using the concept of $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$-open sets. Authors investigated and introduced several basic properties of faintly $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$-continuous functions and almost $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$-continuous functions which are weaker than $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$-continuous functions.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$-open sets, $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$-closed sets, $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$-continuous functions, faintly $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$-continuous functions and almost $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$-continuous functions.</p> <p>AIMS Classification: 54C08, 54C10</p>	

1. INTRODUCTION AND PRELIMINARIES

A crucial area of discussion in general topology is the concept of continuity. Signal and Signal [14] defined almost continuous functions as generalizations of continuity as weaker and stronger types of continuity. In 1978, Popa [7] generalized Signal's notion of virtually continuity by defining almost quasi continuous functions.

In this paper, a new class of weaker forms of $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -continuous functions, known as almost $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -continuous functions was introduced using $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open sets. The examination of a new weaker class of functions known as faintly $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -continuous, along with various characterizations is covered in the next section. Finally, some essential characteristics of almost $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -functions are defined.

Throughout this paper, spaces R and S always means topological spaces (R, τ) and (S, σ) and $f:(R, \tau) \rightarrow (S, \sigma)$ (simply $f: R \rightarrow S$) denotes a function f of a space (R, τ) into a space (S, σ) .

Definition 1.1 [10]: A subset A of a topological space R is called $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed if $\text{spcl}(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $\omega\alpha$ -open in R.

The complement of a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed set is called $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open.

Definition 1.2 [11]: A function f is said to be $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -continuous ($\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -irresolute) if for every open (resp.

$\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open) set V in S, $f^{-1}(V)$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open in R.

Definition 2.1. A function f is called almost continuous [14] (in the sense of Signal) at $r \in R$ if for every open set V in S containing $f(r)$, there $U \in O(R, r)$ with $(U) \subset \text{cl}(\text{int}(V))$. If f is almost continuous at every point of R, then it is called almost continuous.

2. ALMOST $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -CONTINUOUS FUNCTIONS

In this section we introduced almost $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -continuous functions in topological spaces and study some of their basic properties.

Definition 2.1: A function $f: R \rightarrow S$ is said to be almost $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -continuous (a. $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.C) if for each $r \in R$ and $V \in O(S, f(r))$, there exists $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -O(R, r) such that $f(U) \subseteq \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$.

Theorem 2.2: For a function f , the following statements are equivalent:

- (i) f is a. $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.C.
- (ii) for every $V \in RO(S)$, $f^{-1}(V) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -O(R).
- (iii) for every $F \in RC(S)$, $f^{-1}(F) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -C(R).
- (iv) If $A \subset R$, $f(\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(A)) \subseteq \text{cl}\delta(f(A))$.
- (v) If $B \subset S$, $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(f^{-1}(B)) \subset f^{-1}(\text{cl}\delta(B))$.
- (vi) for every $F \in \delta\text{-c}(S)$, $f^{-1}(F) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -C(R).
- (vii) for every $V \in \delta$ -O(S), $f^{-1}(V) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -O(R).

Proof. (i) $\Rightarrow$ (ii) Suppose $V \in RO(S)$ and $r \in f^{-1}(V)$. Then

$f(r) \in V$. As $V \in O(R)$ and f is a. $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$, so $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha-O(R, r)$ with $f(U) \subset \text{int}(\text{cl}(V)) = V$. Thus, $r \in U \subset f^{-1}(f(U)) \subset f^{-1}(V)$ and so, $f^{-1}(V) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha-O(R)$.

(ii) $\Rightarrow$ (v) Let $B \subset S$. Then $f^{-1}(B) \subset S$. By (iv), $f(\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(f^{-1}(B))) \subset \text{cl}\text{-}\delta(f(f^{-1}(B))) \subset \text{cl}(\delta(B))$ and so, $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(f^{-1}(B)) \subset f^{-1}(f(\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(f^{-1}(B)))) \subset f^{-1}(\text{cl}\text{-}\delta(B))$.

(v) $\Rightarrow$ (vi) Let $F \in \delta\text{-}C(S)$, then $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(f^{-1}(F)) \subset f^{-1}(\text{cl}\delta(F)) = f^{-1}(F)$.

So, $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(f^{-1}(F)) = f^{-1}(F)$ and hence $f^{-1}(F) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}C(R)$.

(vi) $\Rightarrow$ (vii) Let $V \in \delta\text{-}O(S)$, then $S - V \in \delta\text{-}C(S)$. By hypothesis, $f^{-1}(S - V) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}C(R)$. Since $f^{-1}(S - V) = R - f^{-1}(V)$, we have $R - f^{-1}(V) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}C(R)$. Thus, $f^{-1}(V) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}O(R)$.

(vii) $\Rightarrow$ (i) Let $r \in R$ and $V \in O(S)$ where $f(r) \in V$. Let us put $W = \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$ and $U = f^{-1}(W)$. As $\text{cl}(V)$ is a closed in S , so $W = \text{int}(\text{cl}(V)) \in \delta\text{-}O(S)$ and from (vii), $U = f^{-1}(W) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}O(R)$. Now, $f(r) \in V = \text{int}(V) \subset \text{int}(\text{cl}(V)) = W$, and so $r \in f^{-1}(W) = U$, $f(U) = f(f^{-1}(W)) \subset W = \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$.

Proposition 2.3: Every a. $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$ is w. $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$.

Proof. Let $r \in R$ and $V \in O(S)$ with $f(r) \in V$. As f is a. $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$, there exists $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}O(R)$ with $r \in U$ and $f(U) \subset \text{int}(\text{cl}(V)) \subset \text{cl}(V)$. Hence, f is w. $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$.

Theorem 2.4: For a function f , the following statements are equivalent:

- (i) f is a. $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$,
- (ii) for each $r \in R$ and $V \in O(S)$ containing $f(r)$, there exists $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}O(R, r)$ with $f(U) \subset \text{cl}(V)$,
- (iii) for each $r \in R$ and $V \in RO(S)$ containing $f(r)$, there exists $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}O(R, r)$ with $f(U) \subset V$.
- (iv) for each $r \in R$ and $V \in \delta\text{-}O(S)$ containing $f(r)$, there exists $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}O(R, r)$ with $f(U) \subset V$.

Theorem 2.5: For a function f , the following statements are equivalent:

- (i) f is a. $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$,
- (ii) $f^{-1}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(V))) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}O(R)$, for every $V \in O(S)$.
- (iii) for every $F \in C(S)$, $f^{-1}(\text{cl}(\text{int}(F))) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}C(R)$.

Proof. (i) $\Rightarrow$ (ii): Let $V \in O(R)$. We need to show that $f^{-1}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(V))) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}O(R)$.

Let $r \in f^{-1}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(V)))$. Then $f(r) \in \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$ and $\text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$ which is a regular open in S . As f is a. $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$, so $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}O(R, r)$ with $f(U) \subset \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$, that is $r \in U \subset f^{-1}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(V)))$. In consequence, $f^{-1}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(V))) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}O(R)$.

(ii) $\Rightarrow$ (iii): Let $F \in C(S)$. Then $S - F \in O(S)$. From (ii), $f^{-1}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(S - F))) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}O(R)$ and $f^{-1}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(S - F))) = f^{-1}(\text{int}(S - \text{int}(F))) = f^{-1}(S - \text{cl}(\text{int}(F))) = R - f^{-1}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(F)))$. Hence $f^{-1}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(F))) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}C(R)$.

(iii) $\Rightarrow$ (i): Let $F \in RC(S)$. Then, $F \in C(S)$. From (iii), $f^{-1}(\text{cl}(\text{int}(F))) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}C(R)$. As $F \in RC(S)$, then $f^{-1}(\text{cl}(\text{int}(F))) = f^{-1}(F)$. Therefore, $f^{-1}(F) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}C(R)$.

By Theorem 3.2, f is a. $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$.

Theorem 2.6: Let f be a. $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$ and $V \in O(S)$. If $r \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}((f^{-1}(V)) - (f^{-1}(V)))$, then $f(r) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(V)$.

Proof. Let $r \in R$ with $r \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}((f^{-1}(V)) - (f^{-1}(V)))$. Suppose $f(r) \notin \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(V)$. Then, $H \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}O(S)$ containing $f(r)$ where $H \cap V = \phi$. So, $\text{cl}(H) \cap V = \phi$, and so $\text{int}(\text{cl}(H)) \cap V = \phi$ and $\text{int}(\text{cl}(H))$ is a regular open in R . As f is a. $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$, $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}O(R, r)$ with $f(U) \subset \text{int}(\text{cl}(H))$. Hence, $f(U) \cap V = \phi$.

However, since $r \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}((f^{-1}(V)) - (f^{-1}(V)))$, $U \cap (f^{-1}(V)) = \phi$ holds for every $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}O(R, r)$, so $f(U) \cap V \neq \phi$, we have a contradiction. Then it follows that $f(r) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(V)$.

Definition 2.7: Let R be a space. A filter base Λ^* is said to be:

- (i) $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -convergent to a point r in R , if for every $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}O(R, r)$, there exists $B \in \Lambda^*$ with $B \subset U$.
- (ii) R -convergent [13] to a point r in R if for every $U \in RO\text{-}(R, r)$, there exists $B \in \Lambda^*$ such that $B \subset U$.

Theorem 2.8: If f is a. $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$, then for each $r \in R$ and filter base Λ^* in R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -converging to r , the filter base $f(\Lambda^*)$ is R -convergent to $f(r)$.

Proof. Let $r \in R$ and Λ^* be any filter base in R , which is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -converging to r . By Theorem 2.6, for any $V \in RO\text{-}(S)$ containing $f(r)$, there exists $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}O(R, r)$ with $f(U) \subset V$.

As Λ^* is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -converging to r , there exists $B \in \Lambda^*$ with $B \subset U$, that is $f(B) \subset V$. Hence the filter base $f(\Lambda^*)$ is R -convergent to $f(r)$.

Definition 2.9: A net (r_λ) is said to be $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -convergent to a point r , if for every $V \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}O(R, r)$, there exists an index λ_0 such that for $\lambda \geq \lambda_0$, $r_\lambda \in V$.

Theorem 2.10: If f is a. $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$, then for each point $r \in R$ and each net (r_λ) which is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -convergent to r , then the net $f((r_\lambda))$ is R -convergent to $f(r)$.

Proof. The proof is similar to that of Theorem 2.7.

Theorem 2.11: If f is a. $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$ injective and S is $r\text{-}T_1$, then R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_1$.

Proof. Suppose S is $r\text{-}T_1$. For any distinct points r and s in R , $f(r) \neq f(s)$. There exist $V, W \in O(R)$ with $f(r) \in V$, $f(s) \notin V$, $f(r) \notin W$ and $f(s) \in W$. As f is a. $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$, $f^{-1}(V)$, $f^{-1}(W) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}O(R)$ with $r \in f^{-1}(V)$, $s \notin f^{-1}(V)$, $r \notin f^{-1}(W)$ and $s \in f^{-1}(W)$, which shows that R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_1$.

Theorem 2.12: If f is a. $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$ injective and S is $r\text{-}T_2$, then R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_2$.

Proof. For any pair of distinct points r and s in R . Then by the injectivity of f , $f(r) \neq f(s)$. There exist disjoint $U, V \in RO\text{-}(R)$ such that $f(r) \in U$ and $f(s) \in V$. As f is a. $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$, $f^{-1}(U) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}O(R, r)$ and $f^{-1}(V) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}O(R, s)$. Thus, $f^{-1}(U) \cap f^{-1}(V) = \phi$, as $U \cap V = \phi$. So R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_2$.

Definition 2.13.: A function f is said to be:

(i) $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -irresolute [11] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open in R for every $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open set V of S .

Definition 2.14: A topological space R is said to be almost regular [10] if for any $F \in \text{RC}(R)$ and any point $r \in R - F$, there exist disjoint $U, V \in \text{O}(R)$ such that $r \in U$ and $F \subset V$.

Theorem 2.15: If f is a $w.\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$ and S is almost regular, then f is a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$.

Proof. Let $r \in R$ and $V \in \text{O}(S, f(r))$. By almost regularity of S , there exists $\text{spg}\omega\alpha \in \text{RO}(S)$ with $f(r) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha \subset \text{cl}(\text{spg}\omega\alpha) \subset \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$. As f is $w.\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$, there exists $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R, r)$ with $f(U) \subset \text{cl}(\text{spg}\omega\alpha) \subset \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$. Thus, f is a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$.

Definition 2.16 [10]: A $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -frontier of a A is denoted by $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-Fr}(A)$, is defined by $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-Fr}(A) = \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(A) \cap \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(R - A)$.

Theorem 2.17: The set of all points $r \in R$ in which a function f is not a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$ is identical with the union of $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -frontier of the inverse images of regular open sets containing $f(r)$.

Proof. Suppose f is not a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$ at $r \in R$. Then there exists $V \in \text{RO}(S)$ containing $f(r)$ such that $U \cap (R - f^{-1}(V)) \neq \emptyset$ for every $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R, r)$. Therefore, $r \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(R - f^{-1}(V)) = R - \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-int}(f^{-1}(V))$ and $r \in f^{-1}(V)$. Thus, $r \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-Fr}(f^{-1}(V))$.

Conversely, suppose f is a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$ at $r \in R$ and $V \in \text{RO}(S)$ containing $f(r)$. Then there exists $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R, r)$ such that $U \subset f^{-1}(V)$, that is $r \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-int}(f^{-1}(V))$. Thus, $r \in R - \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-Fr}(f^{-1}(V))$.

Theorem 2.18: If f is a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$, f^* is $w.\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$ with S is Hausdorff, then the set $\{r \in R: f(r) = f^*(r)\}$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed in R .

Proof. Let $A = \{r \in R: f(r) = f^*(r)\}$ and $r \in R - A$. Then $f(r) \neq f^*(r)$. As S is Hausdorff, there exist $V, W \in \text{O}(S)$ with $f(r) \in V, f^*(r) \in W$ and $V \cap W = \emptyset$. Hence $\text{int}(\text{cl}(V)) \cap \text{cl}(W) = \emptyset$. Since f is a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$, there exists $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R, r)$ with $f(U) \subset \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$. As f^* is $w.\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$, there exists $H \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R)$ such that $f^*(H) \subset \text{cl}(W^*)$. Now put $U = \text{spg}\omega\alpha \cap H$, then $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R, r)$ and $f(U) \cap f^*(U) \subset \text{int}(\text{cl}(V)) \cap \text{cl}(W) = \emptyset$. Therefore, we obtain $U \cap A = \emptyset$ and hence A is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}(R)$.

Theorem 2.19: Suppose the product of two $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open sets is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open. If $f_1: (R_1, \tau) \rightarrow (S, \sigma)$ is $w.\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$, $f_2: (R_2, \tau) \rightarrow (S, \sigma)$ is a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$ and S is Hausdorff, then the set $\{(r_1, r_2) \in R_1 \times R_2 : f_1(r_1) = f_2(r_2)\}$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed in $R_1 \times R_2$.

Proof. Let $A = \{(r_1, r_2) \in R_1 \times R_2 : f_1(r_1) = f_2(r_2)\}$. If $(r_1, r_2) \in (R_1 \times R_2) - A$, then $f_1(r_1) \neq f_2(r_2)$. As S is Hausdorff, there exist disjoint open sets V_1 and V_2 in S with $f_1(r_1) \in V_1$ and $f_2(r_2) \in V_2$ and $\text{cl}(V_1) \cap \text{int}(\text{cl}(V_2)) = \emptyset$. As f_1 (resp.

f_2) is $w.\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$ (resp. a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$), there exists $U_1 \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R_1, r_1)$ such that $f_1(U_1) \subset \text{cl}(V_1)$ (resp. $U_2 \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R_2, r_2)$ with $f_2(\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(U_2)) \subset \text{int}(\text{cl}(V_2))$). Hence, $(r_1, r_2) \in U_1 \times U_2 \subset R_1 \times R_2 - A$. Thus, $(R_1 \times R_2) - A$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open and so A is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed in $R_1 \times R_2$.

3. Faintly $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -Continuous Functions

Definition 3.1: A function $f: R \rightarrow S$ is called faintly $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -continuous (briefly $f.\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$) at a point $r \in R$ if for each $V \in \theta\text{-O}(S, f(r))$, there exists $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R, r)$ such that $f(U) \subseteq V$.

If f has the above property at each point of R , then f is said to be $f.\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$.

Theorem 3.2: The following statements are equivalent for a function f :

- (i) f is $f.\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$
- (ii) for each $V \in \theta\text{-O}(S), f^{-1}(V) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R)$.
- (iii) for each $F \in \theta\text{-C}(S), f^{-1}(F^*) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}(R)$.
- (iv) f is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$.
- (v) for every $B \subseteq S, \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(f^{-1}(B)) \subseteq f^{-1}(\text{cl}\theta(B))$.
- (vi) for every $A \subseteq S, f^{-1}(\text{int}\theta(A)) \subseteq \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-int}(f^{-1}(A))$.

Proof: (i) $\rightarrow$ (ii) Let f be $f.\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$ and $V \in \theta\text{-O}(S)$ such that $r \in f^{-1}(V)$. Then there exists $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R, r)$ with $f(U) \subseteq V$, that is $r \in U \subseteq f^{-1}(V)$. Thus $f^{-1}(V) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R)$.

(ii) $\rightarrow$ (i) Let $r \in R$ and $V \in \theta\text{-O}(S, f(r))$. From (ii), $f^{-1}(V) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R, r)$. Let $U = f^{-1}(V)$, then $f(U) \subseteq V$. Hence f is $f.\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$.

(ii) $\rightarrow$ (iii) Let $V \in \theta\text{-C}(S)$, then $S - V \in \theta\text{-O}(R)$. From (ii), $f^{-1}(S - V) = R - f^{-1}(V) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R)$ and hence $f^{-1}(V) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}(R)$.

(iii) $\rightarrow$ (ii) Let $V \in \theta\text{-O}(S)$, then $S - V \in \theta\text{-C}(S)$. From (iii), $f^{-1}(S - V) = R - f^{-1}(V) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}(S)$ and hence $f^{-1}(V) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R)$.

From the definition 3.1, we can prove the other equivalent properties.

Remark 3.3: Every $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$ is $f.\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$.

Example 3.4: Let $R = \{r_1, r_2, r_3\}$ and $\tau = \{R, \emptyset, \{r_1\}, \{r_2, r_3\}\}$ and $\sigma = \{S, \emptyset, \{r_1\}, \{r_2\}, \{r_1, r_2\}, \{r_2, r_3\}\}$. Then the identity function f is $f.\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$ but not $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$.

Definition 3.5: A function f is said to be weakly $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -continuous (briefly $w.\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$) if for each point $r \in R$ and for each $V \in \text{O}(S, f(r))$, there exists $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R, r)$ such that $f(U) \subset \text{cl}(V)$.

Theorem 3.6: Every weakly continuous function is $f.\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$.

Proof: Let $r \in R$ and $V \in \theta\text{-O}(S, f(r))$. Then there exists $W \in \text{O}(S)$ such that $f(r) \in W \subset V$, that is $f(r) \in W \subset \text{cl}(W) \subset V$. By $w.\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$, there exists $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R)$ such that $f(U) \subset \text{cl}(W)$, that is $f(U) \subset \text{cl}(W) \subset V$. Thus, for each $V \in \theta\text{-O}(S, f(r))$, there exists $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R, r)$ such that $f(U) \subset V$. Hence f is $f.\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$. $\square$

Theorem 3.7: Let f be $\text{f.spg}\omega\alpha.C$ and S is regular space.

Then f is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$.

Proof: Let $V \in O(S)$. As S is regular, $V \in \theta-O(S)$. Since f is $\text{f.spg}\omega\alpha.C$ and from theorem 3.6, $f^{-1}(V) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha-O(R)$. Therefore for every $V \in O(S)$, $f^{-1}(V) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha-O(R)$. Thus f is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$.

Theorem 3.8: Every $\text{f.spg}\omega\alpha.C$ functions is $\text{s.spg}\omega\alpha.C$.

Proof: Let $r \in R$ and V be clopen set in S containing $f(r)$. Then, $V \in \theta-O(S)$. Since f is $\text{f.spg}\omega\alpha.C$, there exists $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha-O(R, r)$ such that $f(U) \subset V$. Thus, for every $V \in \theta-O(S)$, $f(U) \subset V$. Therefore f is $\text{s.spg}\omega\alpha.C$.

Definition 3.9: Let R be TS . Since the intersection of two clopen sets of R is clopen, the clopen sets of R may be use as a base for a topology for R . This topology is called the ultra-regularization of τ and is denoted by τ_u .

A topological space R is said to be ultra-regular if $\tau = \tau_u$.

Theorem 3.10: The following statements are equivalent for a function $f: R \rightarrow S$, if S is ultra-regular space:

- (i) f is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha.C$
- (ii) f is $\text{f.spg}\omega\alpha.C$
- (iii) f is $\text{s.spg}\omega\alpha.C$.

Proof: It follows from the theorem 3.2, 3.8 and definition 3.9.

Definition 3.11: A $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -frontier of a subset A of a space R is defined as

$$\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-Fr}(A) = \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(A) \cap \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(R-A).$$

Theorem 3.12: The set of all points $r \in R$ in which a function f is not $\text{f.spg}\omega\alpha.C$ is the union of $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -frontier of the inverse images of θ -open set containing $\Xi(r)$.

Proof: Suppose f is not $\text{f.spg}\omega\alpha.C$ at each point $r \in R$. Then there exists $V \in \theta-O(S, f(r))$ such that $f(U)$ is not contained in V and hence $r \in \theta\text{-cl}(R - f^{-1}(V))$.

On the other hand, let $r \in f^{-1}(V) \subset \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(f^{-1}(V))$ and hence $r \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(f^{-1}(V))$. Therefore, we can observe that $r \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-fr}(f^{-1}(V))$.

Conversely, assume that f is $\text{f.spg}\omega\alpha.C$ at each point $r \in R$ and $V \in \theta-O(S, f(r))$. Then, there exists $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha-O(R, r)$ such that $U \subset f^{-1}(V)$. Hence $r \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-int}(f^{-1}(V))$. Therefore $r \notin \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-fr}(f^{-1}(V))$.

Theorem 3.13: Let f be a function and $f: (R, \tau) \rightarrow (R \times S, \tau \times \sigma)$ the graph of f defined by $\text{spg}\omega\alpha(x) = (r, f(r))$ for every $r \in R$. If f is $\text{f.spg}\omega\alpha.C$ then f is $\text{f.spg}\omega\alpha.C$.

Proof: Let $U \in \theta-O(S)$, then $R \times U \in \theta-O(R \times S)$. It follows that $f^{-1}(U) = (f)^{-1}(R \times U) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha-O(R, r)$. Hence f is $\text{f.spg}\omega\alpha.C$.

Theorem 3.14: Faintly $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -continuous image of a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -connected space is connected.

Proof: Assume that S is not connected. Then there exist two non-empty open sets V_1 and V_2 such that $V_1 \cap V_2 = \emptyset$ and $V_1 \cup V_2 = S$. Hence $f^{-1}(V_1) \cap f^{-1}(V_2) = \emptyset$ and $f^{-1}(V_1) \cup f^{-1}(V_2) = R$. As f is surjective, $f^{-1}(V_1), f^{-1}(V_2)$ are non-

empty subsets of R . Then $V_1, V_2 \in \theta-O(R)$, since V_1 and V_2 are both open and closed. As f is $\text{f.spg}\omega\alpha.C$, $f^{-1}(V_1), f^{-1}(V_2) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha-O(R)$ and hence R is not $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -connected which is contradiction to the assumption.

Hence S is connected.

Theorem 3.15: If f is $\text{f.spg}\omega\alpha.C$ surjective and R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact then S is θ -compact.

Proof: Let f be $\text{f.spg}\omega\alpha.C$ surjective. Let $\{G_\alpha : \alpha \in \lambda\}$ be any θ -open cover of S . Since f is $\text{f.spg}\omega\alpha.C$, $f^{-1}(G_\alpha)$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover of R . Then there exists a finite subcover $\{f^{-1}(G_i) : i = 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ in R , that is $\{G_i : i = 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ is a subfamily which covers the space S . Thus S is θ -compact.

Theorem 3.16: Let f be $\text{f.spg}\omega\alpha.C$, injective function. If

- (i) S is $\theta-T_1$ then R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha-T_1$
- (ii) S is $\theta-T_2$ then R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha-T_2$

Proof: (i) Let S be $\theta-T_1$. Then for any $r_1, r_2 \in R$ with $r_1 \cap r_2 = \emptyset$, there exists $V_1, V_2 \in \theta-O(S)$ such that $f(r_1) \in V_1, f(r_2) \notin V_1$ and $f(r_1) \notin V_1, f(r_2) \in V_2$. Then $f^{-1}(V_1), f^{-1}(V_2) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha-O(R)$ as f is $\text{f.spg}\omega\alpha.C$ such that $r_1 \in f^{-1}(V_1), r_1 \notin f^{-1}(V_2)$ and $r_2 \notin f^{-1}(V_1), r_2 \in f^{-1}(V_2)$, implies that R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha-T_1$.

(ii) Let S be $\theta-T_2$. Then for any $r_1, r_2 \in R$, there exist $V_1, V_2 \in \theta-O(S)$ such that $f(r_1) \in V_1$ and $f(r_2) \in V_2$. Then $f^{-1}(V_1), f^{-1}(V_2) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha-O(R)$ containing r_1 and r_2 respectively such that $f^{-1}(V_1) \cap f^{-1}(V_2) = \emptyset$ as $V_1 \cap V_2 = \emptyset$. Thus R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha-T_2$.

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